

**COMBINED NON-THERMAL PLASMA AND CATALYTIC OXIDATION OF
LOW CONCENTRATION METHANE**

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ABSTRACT

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This master's thesis studies the effect of non-thermal plasma and the hybridized plasma-catalysis system on the methane abatement by using Dielectric Barrier Discharge (DBD) reactor. The catalysts in the hybridized plasma-catalysis system are found to enhance the selectivity towards carbon dioxide.

The literature part of the thesis presents methane sources, various methods for methane abatement and successful examples related. The effect of different catalysts on methane conversion is also reviewed. Plasma technology specifically the non-thermal plasma chemistry and the plasma effect has been provided in detail.

In the experimental part, the effect of plasma power alone and in the presence of catalysts was studied. Total of seven catalysts were used. The experiments were conducted in DBD reactor at atmospheric pressure having the feed flowrate of 200 ml/min while changing the plasma power and catalysts.

According to the experimental results, the system with only plasma achieved the highest methane conversion 95 %, encompassing both partial and complete oxidation reactions. In contrast, the hybridized system, specifically with 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃, exhibited a slightly lower methane conversion 88 % than the plasma alone system. However, the only reaction that took place in this case was complete oxidation because there was no any carbon monoxide formation. Additionally, there was no noticeable difference observed in the formation of NO_x throughout the study.

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Abbreviations

GHG	GreenHouse Gas
GWP	Global warming potential
IPCC	Intergovernment Panel on Climate Change
NTP	Non-Thermal Plasma
DBD	Dielectric Barrier Discharge
BET	Brunauer-Emmett-Teller
BJH	Barrett-Joyner-Halenda
E-R	Eley-Rideal
FTIR	Fourier Trasnformed Infrared Spectroscopy
GC	Gas Chromatograph
VOC	Volatile Organic compounds
SIE	Specific Input Energy

Symbols

ΔH	Standard enthalpy of reaction (kJ/mol)
U_b	Gas breakdown voltage (V)
P	Plasma power (W)
p	Pressure (bar)
T	Temperature (°C)
Q	Volumetric flowrate (ml/min)
V_l	Molar volume of the ideal gas at STP (dm ³ /mole)
\dot{n}_i	Molar flow of a component (mol/min)
C_i	Molar fraction of a component
X_{CH_4}	Conversion of methane (%)
S_i	Selectivity of a component (%)

1. Introduction

Methane, recognized as a strong greenhouse gas, is widely acknowledged as most influential contributor to the global warming after carbon dioxide (Edenhofer et al., 2015). Starting from 2011, the concentration of methane in the atmosphere has consistently risen, reaching an annual average of 1866 parts per billion in 2019 (Zhai, Panmao. et al., 2021). The increasing trend of methane emissions is a major cause of concern, leading to a heightened interest in comprehending and mitigating its impact (Jackson et al., 2021). Almost 33 % of the overall anthropogenic methane emissions are from the livestock (Zhang et al., 2022).

Several methods are commonly employed to mitigate the atmospheric methane emissions like catalytic oxidation (Epling & Hoflund, 1999). It stands out as a widely adopted and established method for mitigating the methane emissions from coal mines and vehicle exhaust (Monai et al., 2018). Nevertheless, these catalysts are inclined to be deactivated caused by the poisoning and sintering under elevated temperatures (Wang et al., 2015). Meanwhile, to control the emissions from livestock, various livestock management practices are in used like optimizing feed regimes and dietary supplements (Becker et al., 2023).

Another option to oxidize the methane is plasma technology, which has also been investigated by (Da Costa et al., 2008; Pham Huu et al., 2015a, 2015b; Whitehead, 2016, 2019). Specifically cold plasma or non-thermal plasma used in the presence of catalyst in the system to enhance the conversion rate of methane and to refine the product selectivity (Gholami et al., 2022).

This thesis was funded under Horizon Europe project Carbon Neutral Milk (CANMILK), which endeavors to develop an innovative approach utilizing cold plasma and catalysis system to abate methane emissions emanating from cow barns. The focus of this process lies in the conversion of methane into carbon dioxide, since methane has 30 times greater potential of global warming than carbon dioxide (Wang et al., 2023). The principal objective of this thesis revolved around investigating the impact of plasma alone and various catalysts within the plasma system on methane conversion.

The literature part of the thesis diligently expounded upon the comprehensive understanding of methane, methane sources, plasma technology, specifically cold plasma or non-thermal plasma, and reviewing the impact of different catalysts on the conversion of methane.

The experimental phase, on the other hand, was designed to examine the effect of plasma power alone on methane abatement and the effect of catalysts inside the plasma system on methane conversion and subsequent selectivity towards carbon dioxide, while striving to minimize NO_x production. In the experiments, seven catalysts i.e., γ -Al₂O₃, 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃, 3 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃, 1 % Cu/ γ -Al₂O₃, 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al₂O₃, 1 % Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ and 1 % Pd-NH₄ ZSM-5 zeolite were examined.

LITERATURE PART

2. Methane

Methane is a simplest hydrocarbon and the primary component of the natural gas. It is odorless, colorless, and highly flammable. Migeotte in 1948 discovered the methane in atmosphere (Migeotte, 1948). Methane has a much greater warming potential as a greenhouse gas (GHG) than carbon dioxide over a shorter period (Pizzolitto et al., 2019). Globally, the concentration of methane is increasing, and this is not just affecting the climate but also the life on Earth. Over the past 200 years, anthropogenic activities have contributed significant increase in atmospheric methane concentration (Jang et al., 2019). This implies that 0,5 °C of the 1,1 °C increase in atmospheric temperature is because of the methane emissions. The IPCC's sixth assessment report states (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023), an increase in global temperature has resulted in notable modifications to the water cycle, including changes in precipitation patterns, increased evaporation rates, and shifts in the distribution of water resources. Furthermore, it also causes the rise in the sea levels and severity of weather events such as heatwaves, hurricanes, droughts, and heavy rainfalls.

2.1. Atmospheric methane sources

Methane emissions arise from both natural and man-made sources. While natural sources of methane have existed for millions of years, human activities have significantly contributed to the amount of methane in the atmosphere over the past century. The annual global methane emissions are 580 Metric tons CO₂ eq. and emissions from natural sources such as wetlands account for 40 % while the emissions from human activities account for 60 % of the annual emissions globally (Saunois et al., 2020).

Methane is released into the atmosphere in a number of ways: like waste management, agricultural activities, and during the production, transportation, and use of fossil fuels. The main source of emissions caused by humans is agriculture around 55 % and in agriculture sector the largest emissions are from livestock around 34 % (Saunois et al., 2020) as shown in Figure 1. This thesis primarily focuses on the methane emissions from livestock.

■ Energy sector ■ Agriculture sector ■ Waste management ■ Land use

Figure 1 Sources of methane emissions by human activities (Saunois et al., 2020)

2.2. Methane emissions from livestock

Methane emissions from livestock, particularly cattle farming, contribute significantly to methane emissions due to several factors (Tubiello, 2019). Such as cattle populations, their larger size compared to the other livestock animals and their specific digestive physiology makes cattle a noteworthy source of methane emissions within the livestock sector. Methane is released into cow barn air through enteric fermentation, which occurs during digestion in the cow's rumen, and from manure storage and handling (Getabalew et al., 2019). The Food and Agriculture Organization states that, there are 1,5 billion cattle worldwide and 260000 dairy cattle in Finland. The methane emissions from these cows were 30 ktons in the year 2020 in Finland alone (Nations, 2021). Generally, the concentration of methane in a cow barn is 5-100 mg/m³ for milking cow (Melse & van der Werf, 2005). The amount of methane emitted from cow barn air varies depending on a range of factors, such as the diet and management practices of the cows, the type of the barn, and the ventilation system used (Rotz et al., 2010). Addressing and reducing methane emissions from cattle barns have become important area of focus in mitigating GHG and combating climate change.

2.3.Methane abatement

Although nature has its own system to remove the methane from the atmosphere, but it takes 10 years to complete this cycle (Holmes et al., 2013). Moreover, the decomposition of methane indirectly contributes to the ozone depletion. It reacts with the hydroxyl radicals and makes the availability of these radicals limited to breakdown ozone depleting gases (Isaksen et al., 2014). The quest for energy sources and conversion techniques that can provide reduced greenhouse gas emissions in addition to being sustainable fuels has intensified due to the need to protect the environment. There have been intensive studies for the negative impacts of CO₂ but for the CH₄ the research is being conducted recently, usually about removal of methane from known sources rather than atmospheric air. The attempts have been made via various pathways i.e., chemically, physically, and biologically. Using the aerosols in the Fenton technology (Oeste et al., 2017), use of bio-trickling filters (Majdinasab & Yuan, 2017), all have been proven to decrease the methane concentration in the environment. However, the higher costs for these systems and the non-availability of rich methane to run the systems effectively are the main obstacles for their utilization for dilute methane sources including methane emitted from cow barns.

2.4.Methane oxidation

Several techniques are currently being explored for methane oxidation. Methane conversion into useful chemicals and gases, such as the production of syngas through reforming techniques, has been studied (Jagadeesh et al., 2023) as shown in Equation 1, and photocatalysis to CO and other hydrocarbons (W. Li et al., 2018).

Equation 2 depicts the methane oxidation reaction. By using this method, the environmental impact is effectively reduced by over 96 %. (Wei et al., 2022).

Although it is an exothermic reaction ($\Delta H = -801$ kJ/mol) in nature but the bond between C-H is very stable and the need of high energy (439 kJ/mol) to dissociate it makes the overall reaction rate limited (Schwach et al., 2017). Catalysts are commonly employed to facilitate this step by lowering the activation energy (Wen et al., 2022). Still to reach the 100% CH₄ conversion, elevated temperatures (>400 °C) are needed. The drawback of these high

temperatures is that they cause the catalysts to become inactive by increasing the mobility of the catalyst particles over the support of the catalyst (Wang et al., 2023). Thus, there is need to develop novel methods to convert methane while considering these obstacles. As in photocatalytic method, using light energy as a source of energy to oxidize methane into CO₂, the energy needed to activate the methane and reaction temperature can be lowered (Li et al., 2022).

Moreover, the oxidation of methane in the cow barn air is indeed a challenging process due to several factors. Firstly, the low concentration of methane (< 1%), although it is produced in significant amounts by cattle but its concentration in the barn air is relatively low. The barn air contains various other gasses too as shown in the Figure 2 such as carbon dioxide, ammonia, hydrogen sulfide. Some of these are common byproducts of waste and urine or released during respiration or already present in the air. Presence of these gasses can lead to complex interactions and reaction kinetics and can interfere with the oxidation of methane by competing with methane for available energy and radicals. For example, sulfur-containing compounds have been found to exhibit detrimental effects on the catalysts, rendering them poisonous (Zhao et al., 2023). Additionally, water affects the catalyst's activity by interacting with the active sites and converting them into less active species (Coney et al., 2020).

Figure 2 Possible gasses present in the cow barn air (Monroe J.A, 1997)

3. Plasma technology

Plasma technology, an alternative to oxidize the methane, has been widely explored (Da Costa et al., 2008; Pham Huu et al., 2015a, 2015b; Whitehead, 2016, 2019). Use of plasma to mitigate the volatile organic compounds, especially the cold plasma (Vandenbroucke et al., 2011) is among the important applications of the plasma technology. This thesis investigates the abatement of methane using plasma technology as a means of reducing its emissions.

3.1. What is a Plasma?

Ionized gas with an equal concentration of positive and negative ions is called plasma. It can be completely ionized or partially ionized (Snoeckx & Bogaerts, 2017). It can be created by raising the temperature of a gas or by employing several discharge methods that include chambers with electrodes. These chambers can be powered by alternating, pulsed, or direct currents. The breakdown of the gas brought about by these discharges produces a range of species, including ions, electrons, dissociated and excited species, and plasma reactive elements that may possibly result in chemical changes (Magureanu & Bradu, 2022).

Two basic types of plasma are primarily used in industrial operations such as surface modification, destruction of toxic and harmful materials (Bonizzoni & Vassallo, 2002). First one is thermal plasma, which is composed of gas molecules and electrons at extraordinarily high temperatures in a state of thermal equilibrium. In this plasma chemical reactions and transitions happened because of the collisions. The second type, referred as “non-thermal plasma or cold plasma” have the electron temperature between 1 eV and 10 eV higher than those of species or ions present inside the plasma (Eliasson & Kogelschatz, 1991). Electrons have sufficient energy for breaking down the bonds, excitation, and ionization of the species. The majority of research in plasma systems has generally concentrated on the application of non-thermal plasma due to its ability to minimize the catalyst deterioration caused by sintering or coking, as well as its ability to simplify engineering systems. (Nozaki & Okazaki, 2013; Vandenbroucke et al., 2011).

3.1.1. Thermal plasma

To create a thermal plasma a gas is heated to extremely elevated temperatures, typically above $(3-50) \times 10^3$ K, using high-energy sources such as an electric arc, laser, or microwave (Fulcheri, 1995). As these high energy sources provide a high density and hot temperature zone inside the space between the electrodes, the plasma can be generated when gas is passed through it (Bonizzoni & Vassallo, 2002). These electrodes come in a variety of shapes, including two coaxial cylinders, a hollow cylinder, and a cylindrical bar.

There are few types of arc generators for plasma generation. Among them one is, non-transferred arc torch, there is no involvement of the electrodes in the process except the plasma generation. In this type, electrodes are usually cooled with water and most of the arrangements utilize magnetic fields, which are produced by direct current flowing through the electrodes. These torches have the power ranging from 1 kW to 6 MW (Samal & Park, 2012). Then there is transferred arc torch, in which among the two electrodes one electrode is being used externally to allow the arc to transfer to it. This allows the treatment of the substances at extremely elevated thermal fluxes such as metal melting (Bonizzoni & Vassallo, 2002). As thermal plasma has highest energy density, operates at high temperature, produces high flux of radicals in shorter time (Heberlein, 2002). Therefore, it has been used in various applications such as treatment of waste materials, coating of the materials, nano particle synthesis, and in the metallurgical industries (Bonizzoni & Vassallo, 2002).

3.1.2. Non-thermal plasma

Non-thermal plasma (NTP) is the type of plasma when the ions and electrons in the plasma are not in thermal equilibrium. It is produced directly by an electric discharge or by introducing a gas into an electric field. The application of electrical energy to the electrode creates an electric field which provides the activation energy to the flowing gas and then promotes ionization as well as the dissociation of the gas, which produces highly reactive species, neutral molecules, and radicals without any significant increase in the temperature of the gas (Nozaki & Okazaki, 2013).

3.2. Non-thermal plasma chemistry

The complex interplay of electron-ion kinetics, gas phase reactions, and surface interactions inside a plasma allows it to be used for a number of applications. It is important to know about the specific mechanisms and processes occurring within an NTP system. When a gas is introduced in a NTP reactor, the main reactions happening inside, are given below (Eliasson & Kogelschatz, 1991):

- The reactions happening between electron and molecules.

Excitation of molecule	$e^* + C_2$	$C_2^* + e$
Dissociation of molecule	$e + C_2$	$2A + e$
Attachment	$e + C_2$	C_2^-
Dissociative attachment	$e + C_2$	$C^- + C$
Ionization of molecule	$e + C_2$	$C_2^+ + 2e$
Dissociative ionization	$e + C_2$	$C^+ + C + e$
Recombination of molecule	$e + C_2^+$	C_2
Detachment	$e + C_2^-$	$C_2 + e$

- The reactions between atoms and molecules.

Penning dissociation	$N^* + C_2$	$2C + N$
Penning ionization	$N^* + C_2$	$C_2^+ + N + e$
Charge transfer	$C^{+*} + D$	$D^{+*} + C$
Ion recombination	$C^- + D^+$	CD
Neutral recombination	$C + D + N$	$CD + N$

- Electronic and atomic decomposition

Electronic	$e + CD$	$C + D + e$
Atomic	$C^* + D_2$	$CD + D$

- Electronic and atomic synthesis

Electronic	$e + C$	$C^* + e$
	$C^* + D$	CD
Atomic	$C + D$	CD

In this case, the gas atoms are C and D, its molecules are C₂ and D₂, its energized electron is e*, and its transient collision species is N. The ionic species are marked with negative and positive charges, and excited species are marked with (*). The initial stage involves electron collisions, which induce the activation of atoms and molecules present in the gas. Subsequently, these excited species engage in reactions and facilitate the transfer of charge and energy, thereby stimulating and exciting the other species. This cascade effect perpetuates the chain of activation and excitation.

Non-thermal plasma technology has been viewed as an attractive substitute for traditional thermal or catalytic methods due to its non-equilibrium nature, low energy consumption, and exceptional capacity to start physical and chemical reactions at low temperatures for gas purification and atmospheric pollution removal (Bruggeman et al., 2010) (Vandenbroucke et al., 2011).

The configuration of plasma setup usually consists of an electrode, the injected gas, and a power source. The change in the gas composition and altering the power of the plasma can have noticeable effect on the energy yield of these devices (Chandana et al., 2018b). NTP can be categorized into groups based on the method employed to generate them. Some important plasma discharges and their typical parameters are provided in the Table 1. As the focus of this study revolves around the utilization of silent discharge which is also named as dielectric barrier discharge.

Table 1 Typical parameters of different NTP discharges (Eliasson et al., 1991)

Parameters	Glow Discharge	Corona Discharge	Silent Discharge
Pressure (bar)	< 0,01	1	1
Electric-field (kV/cm)	0,01	0,5-50	0,1-100
Electron energy (eV)	0,5-2	5	1-10
Ionization degree	10 ⁻⁶ -10 ⁻⁵	N.A	10 ⁻⁴
Electron density (cm⁻³)	10 ⁸ -10 ¹¹	10 ¹³	10 ¹⁴

3.3. Dielectric barrier discharge

Theodore du Moncel was the first to realize that plasma could be created at atmospheric pressure utilizing dielectric barriers spanning two electrodes. It has history dating back to its use in ozone synthesis (Kogelschatz, 2003). Dielectric barrier discharge or DBD is a highly versatile, efficient technology to produce non-thermal plasma and it offers scalability, flexibility, and stable plasma generation. Additionally, its fundamental chemical and physical properties are well understood. Usually, two types of DBD configurations, planar and cylindrical, are used.

Figure 3 Planar (top) and coaxial (bottom) reproduced from (Snoeckx & Bogaerts, 2017)

In Figure 3, a basic planar and cylindrical configurations of a dielectric barrier discharge reactor is shown. Both configurations consist of one ground electrode, live electrode, and dielectric barrier. The barrier is used to avoid the formation of sparks and arcs. The flow is applied in the discharge gap between the electrode and dielectric barrier. It ranges from 1 mm to 1 cm without any loss in the plasma efficiency (Hammer, 2000). Mostly, DBD operates at lower temperature and pressure is atmospheric. Plasma is generated by breakdown of the gas, and it depends on the applied voltage, U_b which is determined by the Paschen's law as shown in Eq. 3 (Snoeckx & Bogaerts, 2017).

$$U_b = \frac{Dpd}{\ln\left(\frac{C_{pd}}{\ln\frac{1}{\gamma}}\right)} \quad (3)$$

In Equation 3, D is related to the ionization and excitation energy, γ is the electron emission coefficient, C is the saturated ionization in the gas, p is the pressure of the gas and d is the gap between the electrodes.

There are three steps in the growth of discharge (Wong, 2016):

- Pre-breakdown:
A negative space charge as electrons gets collected at anode. The enough generation of electric field to breakdown the gas. It lasts for 0,5 ms.
- Propagation:
This depends on the wave of the ionization from anode to cathode. Ions and electron pairs are formed during the wave. It takes 1-2 ns.
- Decay:
This is the charge build up on dielectric material which balances the external applied voltage. Usually, the micro discharge only lasts for few nanoseconds. As the amount of energy given and the charge provided to the micro discharge are restricted by dielectric material. That's why it produces cold plasma.

Dielectric barrier discharge broadly studied for various applications like reduction of NO_x , removal of odor, and air pollution control (Quoc An et al., 2011). While plasma technology offers numerous advantages, it is important to address the challenges of high energy consumption and non-selectivity of products. Researchers have been concentrating on integrating plasma with various techniques over the past two decades (Magureanu & Bradu, 2022). One such combination that has garnered significant attention is plasma-catalysis, which is the focus of the current study. By leveraging plasma-catalysis, attempts are being made to overcome the challenges and enhance the energy efficiency and selectivity. In the study by (De Rosa et al., 2022), demonstrated that the addition of a catalyst to the plasma system can lower the specific input energy (SIE) needed to achieve the same level of carbon dioxide yield or methane conversion. It has been noted that the specific input energy of a plasma-catalytic system is two to three times lower when catalyst is present than in a plasma alone system.

4. Catalysts in plasma processes

4.1. Catalyst for methane complete oxidation

Numerous catalysts have been reported to be used in various plasma-assisted catalysis processes; however, the best catalyst to choose for a given plasma-catalysis system is still unknown. In short, catalyst should adsorb the reagents and create the pathways that will get the required conversion and products and avoid the formation of byproducts. So far, after reading the literature and studies, it has been seen that all the catalysts, that are proved to be suitable for a hybrid system, are used in the thermal catalytic systems for the same processes.

The metals such as palladium, platinum, rhodium, has been reported for the oxidation of methane in both systems, thermal as well as in plasma. Palladium metal is well known for the methane oxidation at lower temperatures. In Eq. 4, the mechanism of the methane oxidation on a catalyst having the Pd metal is explained by (Nkinahamira et al., 2023). The pathway to produce carbon dioxide: CH₄ adsorbs on the surface and gives CH₃ radical, then the formation of formate happens and oxidation of formates into carbonates by surface oxygen and finally gives carbon dioxide.

Pd supported on alumina (Pd/Al₂O₃) has been used to convert methane (Pham Huu et al., 2015a). Different amounts of loading of Pd were used. For an inlet methane concentration of 500 ppm, it was found that the methane conversion increased from 35 % to 55 % when the loading of metal increased from 0,5 to 1%. The availability of more reactive sites on the catalyst surface could be the underlying reason. In the study by Yao, at room temperature in plasmas-catalysis system, when Al₂O₃ was used as catalyst, the methane conversion was prevented by the generation of carbonates on the surface of the catalyst but when Au metal was introduced, the bidentate carbonates decomposed into gaseous CO₂ (Yao et al., 2019). In a study by (Dong et al., 2023), a dielectric barrier discharge reactor was used having the Pd/ZrO₂/Al₂O₃ catalysts to oxidize the lean concentration of methane (0,3 %). Various loadings (5 %, 10 % and 30 %) of ZrO₂ were used to check the effect and it was found that the ZrO₂ loading enhanced the CH₄ oxidation (85% to almost 98%) and the CO₂ selectivity by converting surface formate.

In this thesis, the primary objective is to address the mitigation of methane, but also taking in account the minimization of byproducts such as NO_x . Consequently, the emphasis lies on identifying the catalysts that exhibit dual functionality.

4.2. Effect of supports on methane activation

The activation of the methane is noticeably impacted by the particle size and characteristics of the supporting material (Nilsson et al., 2015). Some commonly used support material for oxidation of methane are alumina, silica, zeolites, and mixed metal oxides. To decrease the amount of metal present and to improve the dispersion of the metal and stability of the metal, the catalyst active sites are deposited onto supports (Jiang et al., 2020). This improved metal dispersion is crucial for catalyst performance, as it ensures a higher number of metal atoms are exposed to the reactant species.

The effect of various zeolite supports on the oxidation of methane has been reviewed by (H. Y. Chen et al., 2022). Typically, the principal species to activate the methane in a palladium-based catalyst is the PdO. The production of PdO can be enhanced by selecting support materials with high tendency of adsorbing oxygen. Zeolites with high Si/Al ratio proved to be fell under this category (Friberg et al., 2021). These are crystalline aluminosilicate materials having a well-defined microporous structure. The high surface area, shape selectivity, and acidity (adjustable) properties make it suitable support for methane activation. That's why, when Pd is dispersed and stabilized on the zeolites, the catalytic activity increased. The relationship between silica and alumina ratio, Pd supported on different zeolites frames and the oxidation of methane is explained by (Friberg et al., 2021). Its noteworthy that the specific effects of increasing the silica and alumina ratio can vary depending on the kind of zeolite. According to their findings, the selection of zeolite support is important for both promoting the generation of well-dispersed Pd particles and minimizing the generation of ion exchanged Pd species. Small pore zeolites and a high Si/Al ratio can be used to achieve this.

5. Plasma-catalysis

Plasma-catalysis, also known as plasma-assisted catalysis, involves combining a gaseous discharge or plasma with catalysts. This can be done by various methods. This hybridization can give results with improved outcomes which cannot be possible to get while using plasma system and catalytic system separately. You can see the various applications of this hybridized system in the Figure 4.

Figure 4 Various applications of the plasma-catalysis system (Kim et al., 2016b)

Unlike thermal catalysis, where reactive species form exclusively on the surface of the heated catalyst, in plasma-catalysis, these reactive species can be generated in the gas phase through dissociation within the plasma or subsequent reactions of plasma-excited species. (Whitehead, 2016). This highlights a distinct mechanism that extends beyond traditional thermal catalytic processes.

5.1. Coupling of plasma and catalyst

Generally, plasma and catalyst can be coupled in one of two ways as mostly described in different studies (Khoja et al., 2019). When the catalyst material is introduced straight into the plasma zone, it is known as “In-plasma catalyst system” as shown in Figure 5. The catalyst is inserted after the plasma zone, it is called “post-plasma catalyst system” as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5 One stage setup

Figure 6 Two stage setup

After applying the voltage, the formation of radicals and active species happened as already describe in Chapter 3.2. The lifetime of these reactive species or radicals is the important parameter to examine the feasibility of these systems. Since a ground state oxygen atom in an NTP has a lifetime of about 14 μs (Holzer, 2002). This implies that the species will only be able to react in a very small area or boundary layer. Many studies have employed both configurations to examine the feasibility and have consistently demonstrated that the combination of one stage plasma-catalysis is the more favorable option (Drake et al., n.d.; Kim et al., 2016a). For example, in the work by (Quoc An et al., 2011), a plasma-catalysis system was used to abate toluene from the atmosphere with both arrangements, post-plasma, and in-plasma. In-plasma configuration showed up to 96 % toluene conversion while post plasma showed 80 % conversion.

5.2. Hybridization effect of the plasma-catalysis system

In the investigation conducted by (Costa et al., 2008), Pd supported on alumina ($\text{Pd}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) was tested in a DBD reactor having the mixture of gases (CH_4 , O_2 , CO_2 , and NO) and nitrogen as a balance gas. It was observed that the methane conversion started when temperature was 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ in the absence of catalyst but when catalyst was present the methane conversion was almost 100 % at the same temperature. The integration of plasma and catalysis offers unique advantages by harnessing the active species formed by plasma and the specific reactivity of catalyst for selectivity. The possible effects of plasma-catalysis system are shown in Figure 7.

Effect of plasma on catalyst	Synergy	Effect of catalyst on plasma
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enlarge surface area • Modify surface reactions • Modify activation barrier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prolong catalyst stability • Increase product selectivity • Enhance energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change discharge behaviour • Low activation barrier • Prolong the lives of active species

Figure 7 Possible effects of plasma-catalysis system (Khoja et al., 2019)

There have been conflicts about the synergy effects of this modified system like in one study, it is argued that the catalyst only promotes the CO oxidation (Baylet et al., 2012). DBD reactor was used to breakdown the mixture of 0,3 % to 1 % CH₄ (CO₂/N₂/O₂/H₂O) and to generate the plasma. No significant difference was observed in the methane conversion but the CO₂ selectivity upon introducing the catalyst was increased. While in other study, by (Lee et al., 2015), the effective synergy of the plasma coupled with catalyst for CH₄ conversion was observed. They used a dielectric barrier discharge reactor to perform the complete oxidation of the methane in an in-plasma arrangement. Palladium as an active metal supported on different materials was used as a catalyst. Even when there was no any catalyst placed the methane beginning to convert into CO and CO₂ but the selectivity for CO₂ was lower. When catalyst was introduced, the selectivity of the CO₂ increased, and it showed the complete oxidation of the methane. The reaction mechanism inside plasma-catalysis configuration is shown Eq. 5 to 10.

Equations 5 and 6 illustrate how the collisions between the energy-rich electrons and methane caused the two elements to dissociate, forming methyl and oxygen radicals. CO, H₂O, and CO₂ were produced by the reaction of oxygen radicals with methyl and hydroxyl

radicals as well as hydrogen. (Kim et al., 2016b) also reported the direct Eley-Rideal mechanism inside the plasma-catalysis system. Radicals generated by plasma directly reacted with the oxygen which is adsorbed onto the surface of the catalyst. C-H bond dissociation was observed to be rate determining step, it was also found that the methane, which is vibrationally excited by plasma, is the key species to promote the methane conversion in the modified system (Nozaki & Okazaki, 2013). As it has the greatest electron collision cross section. It has the potential to boost the catalyst's dissociative chemisorption, which would raise conversion.

In the study by (Stere et al., 2020), in NTP system the formation of surface formate over Pd/Al₂O₃ was observed via IR which subsequently decomposed to form CO and CO₂. Unlike thermal catalysis, the formation of surface formate is predominant in a NTP system, and the role of palladium could be to form oxygen active species and increase the decomposition of the species adsorbed on the support such as formate and in result facilitate the carbon dioxide yield. Recently, (Dong et al., 2023) also observed the same phenomenon for the oxidation of lean methane (0,3 %) in a DBD reactor. At lower temperature the dissociation took place and converted methane and oxygen into methyl radicals and O atom by the NTP plasma. O reacted with O₂ and formed O₃. Methyl radical got adsorbed on to surface of the catalyst and oxidized by the oxygen present on the surface of the catalyst, into surface formate and water. That water reacted with O species at higher temperature and produce OH. The catalyst functioned when temperature is 300 °C and promoted the further oxidation of formate present on the surface to CO₂ and water.

NO_x production was also recorded by chromatographic analysis (Baylet et al., 2012). As nitrogen and oxygen were present in the reactant gas mixture, the generation of the O and N species by plasma reacted with each other and formed these byproducts as shown in the Eq. 11 to 16.

6. Plasma operation

Understanding, the impact of plasma operations on the conversion is a complex and multifaceted process. The interplay of various parameters, including plasma power, gas composition, and reactant characteristics needs to be carefully controlled and optimized to achieve desired conversion efficiency and selectivity.

6.1. The effect of input power

The impact of input plasma power also studied. Higher input power can enhance the generation of plasma (Nozaki & Okazaki, 2013). This results in a greater number of highly energetic electrons, ultimately facilitating the dissociation of methane and formation of reactive species. Generally, when the power is increased, it can enhance the overall conversion but the relationship between power and conversion can also be nonlinear at higher voltages (Gholami et al., 2022). During the experiments, when the specific input energy (SIE) was increased from 1 to 4 (J/mL) the CH₄ conversion improved from 0 to 90 %. In another study (Stere et al., 2020), NTP-assisted oxidation of methane over Al₂O₃ is investigated by using dielectric barrier discharge reactor. In the mass spectroscopy analysis, it was observed that when plasma voltage was raised from 5 to 6 kV, the methane conversion also increased. It was 27 % at 5 kV and reached to 42 % when voltage was 6 kV.

The effect of power on NO_x formation was also examined. At higher SIE, the NO_x formation is mainly NO, as an increased in the electric impact resulted in the formation of radicals (N, O, CH₃). Different catalysts were examined to assess their impact on NO_x formation and CH₄ conversion. However, it was observed that simultaneous reduction of NO_x and oxidation of CH₄ proved to be challenging due to the nitrogen and oxygen presence in the reactant gas mixture. The presence of oxygen led to a diminutive effect on NO_x removal. This outcome can be attributed to the dissimilar dissociative energies of O₂ and N₂, combined with the relatively low average electron kinetic energy of the NTP reactor. Oxygen has dissociative energy of 4,8 eV, nitrogen has 9,2 eV (Khacef & Da Costa, 2019). NTP can readily dissociate the O₂ molecules into oxygen atoms which can then engage with the nitrogen to generate NO_x as shown in the section 5.2 (Equations 11, 12, 15 and 16).

6.2. The effect of gas composition

The effect of the feed composition is also examined in various studies. When Argon used as a balance gas with CH₄ and O₂, it is noted that excited Ar can dissociate the methane and oxygen by transferring energy to them (Gholami et al., 2022). The conversion of the methane was higher (97,7 %) in a simple mixture (CH₄, O₂) while it was 89,7 % for the complex mixture (CH₄, CO₂, O₂, H₂O and N₂). It can be because of the generation of too many excited species and different by products in the DBD reactor after applying the voltage. When N₂ used as balance gas in the mixture of methane and carbon dioxide, the dissociation of methane was augmented by the electron impact excitation of N₂ and resulted in the increased methane conversion and carbon dioxide conversion (Wang et al., 2018).

6.3. The effect of temperature

In most of the plasma catalysis setups, an elevation in temperature typically leads to improve the conversion. This pattern can be ascribed to an augmented reaction pace between atomic oxygen or hydroxyl radicals and exposed gasses (Hayashi et al., 2009). In cases where electron impact dominates over radical interactions, no correlation with temperature detected because electron density has minimal temperature dependency (Harling et al., 2007). Nonetheless, a temperature increase can still enhance pollution abatement by boosting the overall energy density (Huang et al., 2001). In the investigation by (Baylet et al., 2012), in the plasma-catalysis system the conversion of methane at room temperature was 15 % while at 200 °C temperature the conversion was 25 % at constant plasma power and gas flowrate.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

7. Materials and methods

In this chapter, we delve into the experimental investigations conducted to study the effects of cold plasma on methane abatement. The objective of this study was to examine the oxidation of dilute methane (1 vol. %) into carbon dioxide using non-thermal plasma. Additionally, the impact of various catalysts to system performance was also studied. The experiments were carried out at VTT Technical Research Center of Finland using DBD reactor.

Experiments were guided by two main research questions: The first objective was, to distinct the direct influence of cold plasma on methane conversion to CO₂. This was studied by adjusting the plasma power across different levels to understand its impact comprehensively. The next phase was to examine the synergistic effect of cold plasma in combination with catalysts. By employing different catalysts and varying the plasma power, we aimed to understand if and how the catalytic process could be enhanced or modulated with the assistance of plasma.

7.1. Catalysts

Several catalysts were prepared by VTT for the experimentation for this study. The list of the catalysts is presented in the Table 2. Two types of support materials were used, gamma alumina and NH₄-ZSM-5 to investigate their respective impacts on the reactions. Pure gamma alumina support was also tested in the experiments.

Impregnation method was employed for catalyst preparation. In this process, the γ -Al₂O₃ spheres were impregnated with specific metal precursors. Nitrate salts served as the chosen precursors in this context. After the impregnation, the spheres underwent a calcination process. The impregnated γ -Al₂O₃ spheres shared a consistent size range, with diameters falling between 3,5 to 4 mm. This consistency ensures that the sphere size remains a constant parameter.

Table 2 Catalysts tested in this study.

	Catalyst
1	γ -Al ₂ O ₃
2	1 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃
3	1 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃
4	1 % Pt/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃
5	1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃
6	3 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃
7	1 % Pd-NH ₄ ZSM-5

7.2. Catalyst characterization

N₂ Physisorption

The physisorption experiments for catalyst characterization were conducted using a Micromeritics 3Flex 3500 instrument, ensuring accurate measurements and repeatability. An accurately weighed catalyst sample, approximately 0,25 g, was prepared. The sample was placed inside an empty clean sample tube. Before analysis, catalyst sample subjected to a thorough degassing procedure. Here sample was exposed to a temperature of 200 °C for the period of 16 h. It was crucial to remove any adsorbed gases or contaminants from the catalyst sample. This step ensured that measurements taken were solely due to the N₂ gas used in the analysis, without interference from other adsorbed species. Once degassing was complete, the sample tube, now containing the prepared catalyst, was carefully mounted onto the Micromeritics 3Flex 3500 equipment. A cryogenic storage unit, filled with liquid nitrogen, was positioned directly beneath the sample tube. The rapid evaporation and cold temperature of the liquid nitrogen created the desired cryogenic conditions for the N₂ gas to physically adsorb onto the surface of the catalyst.

When the physisorption was conducted, the data processing and analysis of the resulting isotherms were carried out using the MicroActive software. This software facilitates precise calculations from the raw data, ensuring accurate interpretations of the properties of the material. Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method specializes in determining the volume of

pore and distribution of the size of mesoporous materials. The BJH method involves analyzing the desorption segment of a nitrogen isotherm. From the isotherm, it calculates the volume of gas adsorbed within pores of a specific diameter as the relative pressure changes. The primary result derived from this method for our studies was the pore volume.

Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method is an accepted technique for determining the area of surface of solid materials. By analyzing the physical adsorption of nitrogen gas on a solid surface (typically at the boiling temperature of the adsorbate), the BET method calculates the total surface area, considering multilayer adsorption. From this method, surface area and pore diameter were calculated.

7.3. Test rig

The reaction experiments were conducted in a laboratory-scale rig, coupled with a cold plasma or DBD reactor. Figures 8 and 9 show the experimental setup schematic and a photo of the DBD reactor respectively.

The DBD reactor was constructed from the two co-axial quartz tubes. The plasma discharges were created by applying power between inner (high voltage) and outer (ground) electrodes, both being 2 cm long. In this configuration, the outer electrode served as a ground electrode and was composed of stainless-steel mesh. The surface of the outer electrode was covered with Kapton tape. The inner electrode, a stainless-steel metal rod, was connected to the reactor from the bottom. The inner electrode was connected to the power source. The power was supplied by a power source (PVM500) having the range 10-300 W. The plasma power was measured online and determined by external capacitor method with MATLAB-based calculation software. In this work, a 22 nF capacitor was used. The precise flow of the reactant gas mixture (1 vol. % CH₄ in balanced air) fed into the DBD reactor, was maintained by Bronkhorst mass flow controllers. The product gases were directed to a water-cooled condenser after undergoing the reaction in the DBD reactor. This step trapped and removed water from the product stream, ensuring that only the desired gases proceeded to the gas flow meter, where the flowrate of the gas was measured. The gas then routed for real time analysis with FTIR (Gasmeter FTIR Analyzer) and Agilent micro-Gas Chromatograph (490 μ GC) instrument. After analysis, the effluent gases were safely directed to a designated vent, ensuring no accumulation of produced gases or back-pressure in the system and adherence to safety protocols.

Figure 8 Schematic diagram of the experiment setup. MFC (Mass flow controller). GFM (Gas Flow Meter)

Figure 9 Picture of DBD reactor while connected to the rig.

7.4. Packing of the catalyst inside the DBD reactor

The catalyst was placed inside the DBD reactor as shown in Figures 10 and 11. Specifically, the empty space (4 mm) between the ground electrode and the high voltage electrode, was filled with the catalytic material, making certain that the catalyst and plasma interact as best they can. These experiments are referred as `in-plasma` configuration in the following text. To ensure stability and to prevent the catalyst from moving, quartz wool was employed to create a bed just outside the reactor's discharge zone, holding the packing securely in place as shown in Figure 10. The rationale and benefits behind opting for this configuration, as opposed to other possible setup (Post plasma), have been discussed in Chapter 5.1.

Figure 10 Picture of the DBD reactor with 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ catalyst (blue granules) packed over the quartz wool. The outer electrode (metal mesh) is placed at the lower part of the reactor for the photo.

Figure 11 Scheme of the DBD reactor. Purple area showing the plasma zone where catalyst placed. The rod which is coming from the bottom is inner electrode and the outer electrode is placed on the purple area.

7.5. Experimental conditions

A mixture comprising 1 % CH₄ balanced with air was used as feed for the study. The composition of the feed gas is given in the Table 3. Experiment conditions are given in the Table 4. The reactant gas mixture was maintained at a continues flow rate of 200 ml/min. Different plasma power levels were tested to study their impact on the reaction. Specifically, the experiments were conducted at power levels of 15 W, 20 W, 25 W, and 30 W. Throughout these variations, the flow rate of the gas mixture was kept consistent. Each experiment was carried out two to three times. This repetition aimed to check for the possible uncertainty, such as potential inconsistencies in the packing of the reactor. In the experiments where the effect of catalyst was tested, 1,2 g of the sample was packed inside the reactor as depicted in the previous section 7.4.

Table 3 Feed gas composition

Gas	CH ₄ (vol-%)	O ₂ (vol-%)	N ₂ (vol-%)
Concentration	0,99	20,89	78,12

Table 4 Experiment conditions.

Factor	Description
Plasma discharge gap size (mm)	4
Plasma discharge length (cm)	2
Tested plasma power (W)	15, 20, 25, 30
Feed gas composition (vol. %)	0,99 % CH ₄ , 20,89 % O ₂ , 78,12 % N ₂
Gas flow rate (ml/min)	200
Temperature °C	40-200 (No external heating)
Pressure	Atmospheric

7.6. Execution of the experiments

Before conducting the reaction experiments, a pressure test was performed using N₂ gas. This step was crucial to ensure the system was sealed correctly and that there were no leakages. Blank measurements were also taken prior to the plasma ignition. In the blank measurement, the reactant gas was passed through the system without turning on the plasma system, to get the initial concentration of the reactant gas and the flowrate of the gas. These measurements provided a reference point, allowing for accurate determination of the feed concentration in subsequent experiments. After taking the readings, the plasma system was switched on. All experiments were carried out at atmospheric pressure. No external heating was applied during the experiments, ensuring the observed results were purely due to the plasma and catalyst interactions. The reactor outside temperature was measured with an Infrared thermometer. For each setpoint, the measurements were taken when FTIR and μ GC readings were stabilized, to minimize any fluctuation and errors in the readings. Stabilized reading was the indication that the system was now consistent and steady state. For a setpoint to be completed, it took one to one and half hours for the steady state readings.

7.7. Product analysis

7.7.1. Plasma power calculation

The evaluation of each experiment was carried out by analyzing data sourced from multiple instruments. When plasma was switched on and adjusted to the desired power with the help of PVM500 power source, TiePie Engineering Handyscope HS6 Oscilloscope was used to monitor the various parameters which include input voltage, voltage over the capacitor and

the current. In this work, a 22 nF capacitor was used. The plasma power was measured online and determined by external capacitor method with MATLAB-based calculation software. For each setpoint, plasma power was stabilized around 25 to 40 minutes. In the Figure 12, an example of the stabilization of the plasma power is showed.

Figure 12 Plasma power monitored with MATLAB-based calculation software created by VTT.

7.7.2. Analytical methods

A Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (Gaset FTIR Analyzer) was employed for real-time analysis of the gas products specifically for NO_x and N₂O. It offered a comprehensive spectral overview, enabling the identification of various gas compounds present.

To further refine the analysis and gain more detailed insights into the product composition including CH₄, O₂, N₂, CO₂, CO and H₂, an Agilent micro-Gas Chromatograph (490 μGC) was used. The online connection ensured timely data capture.

7.7.3. Calculation methods

To quantify and interpret the reaction results, the results of the μGC and FTIR analysis were integrated with quantitative calculations. The ideal gas law was used in the calculations to determine the molar flows of the reactants and products. The molar flow of methane is computed in Equation 17.

$$\dot{n}_{\text{CH}_4} = C_{\text{CH}_4} \times \frac{Q_{\text{in}}}{V_I} \quad (17)$$

where

\dot{n}_{CH_4} is the CH₄ molar flow in the feed.

C_{CH_4} is the CH_4 molar fraction in the feed.

V_1 is the ideal gas molar volume at STP (22,7 dm³/mol)

Q_{in} is the flowrate of the reactant gas at normal condition.

The molar flowrates of other gasses and the products were calculated in the same way. For products the out flowrate was used. The conversion rate of CH_4 , which is an indication of how much of the initial CH_4 feed has reacted or been transformed in the experimental process, was calculated by the Equation 18. The equations 19, 20, and 21 provided the selectivity towards CO_2 , CO , and carbon balance.

$$CH_4 \text{ conversion } (X_{CH_4} \%) = \left[\frac{n_{CH_4 \text{ in}} - n_{CH_4 \text{ out}}}{n_{CH_4 \text{ in}}} \times 100 \right] \quad (18)$$

$$CO_2 \text{ selectivity } (S_{CO_2} \%) = \left[\frac{n_{CO_2 \text{ produced}}}{n_{CH_4 \text{ converted}}} \times 100 \right] \quad (19)$$

$$CO \text{ selectivity } (S_{CO} \%) = \left[\frac{n_{CO \text{ produced}}}{n_{CH_4 \text{ converted}}} \times 100 \right] \quad (20)$$

$$\text{Carbon balance } (\%) = \left[\frac{n_{CH_4 \text{ out}} + n_{CO_2 \text{ out}} + n_{CO \text{ out}}}{n_{CH_4 \text{ in}}} \times 100 \right] \quad (21)$$

8. Results and discussions

This chapter contains, the outcomes and analyses derived from the catalyst characterization and plasma-assisted catalysis experiments. Throughout this chapter, the data, graphs, and the interpretations will explain the interplay between catalyst properties and plasma conditions, painting a picture of using plasma-assisted catalysis for methane abatement.

8.1. Catalyst characterization

N₂ Physisorption

These measurements were done for fresh catalysts and few spent catalysts. There was some technical problem with the instrument later, so only few spent catalysts were characterized. Table 5 shows the physisorption results for catalysts, displaying their pore volume, surface area, and pore size.

Table 5 Pore size, pore volume and surface area of the catalysts examined by BJH desorption isotherm.

Fresh catalyst	BET surface area (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore size (nm)
γ -Al ₂ O ₃	231	0,60	10
1 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	263	0,63	10
3 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	228	0,59	10
1 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	227	0,60	10
1 % Pd-0.5 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	225	0,60	10
1 % Pt/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	228	0,59	10
1 % Pd-NH ₄ ZSM-5	566	0,30	2
Spent catalyst			
1 % Pd/ γ - Al ₂ O ₃	259	0,63	10
1 % Cu/ γ - Al ₂ O ₃	224	0,60	10
1 % Pd-NH ₄ ZSM-5	508	0,27	2

When the metals, such as Pd, Pt and Cu, were added to γ -Al₂O₃, it showed a decreasing trend in the pore volume and surface area of the catalysts. But 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst exhibited a relatively high pore volume and surface area compared to other catalysts. The zeolite supported 1% Pd-NH₄ ZSM-5 displayed a significantly higher surface area but has a much smaller pore size and lower pore volume. To assess the influence of plasma on the catalyst

surface, physisorption experiments were conducted on several spent catalysts. The results of these experiments indicated that there was no significant difference in the surface areas of the catalysts suggesting that the plasma treatment had no appreciable effect on the structural characteristics of the catalysts except 1 % Pd-NH₄ ZSM-5 for which the surface area reduced to 508 m²/g from 566 m²/g.

8.2. Results for only plasma system

To look into how plasma power affects the conversion of methane, experiments were conducted using only plasma, without the presence of a catalyst. Throughout the experiments, the feed flowrate was kept constant at 200 ml/min, while adjusting the plasma power across various levels. This approach ensured that any observed changes in methane conversion were solely attributable to the variations in plasma power, eliminating flow rate as a variable factor. These μ GC results in Table 6 from the Experiment 03 and 06 using the Reactor A. The details about all the experiments can be found in the Appendix 1.

Table 6 μ GC results from experiment 03 and 06 using plasma alone system

Power	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20 W	0,97	20,7	76,7	0,55	20,26	77,3	0,18	0,23	0,05
25 W	0,97	20,7	76,7						
30 W	0,97	20,7	76,7	0,06	19,32	78,2	0,61	0,30	0,00
20 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,51	20,11	77,5	0,17	0,24	0,03
25 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,09	19,26	77,7	0,54	0,30	0
30 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,06	19,17	77,9	0,64	0,25	0

The Figure 13 is showing the effect of plasma power on the conversion of methane. At the lowest plasma power of 15 W, there was no conversion of CH₄. This suggested that this power level was insufficient to ignite the reaction and activate the methane. At 20 W, there's a noticeable CH₄ conversion rate of approximately 59 %. Increasing the plasma power to 25 W significantly enhances the CH₄ conversion to 92 %. At the highest power setting of 30 W, CH₄ conversion further increases to 95 %. The results clearly demonstrated the impact of power on the conversion of methane. As the power increases, the conversion of CH₄ improves. This phenomenon can be described by the fact that as power increased, there is a corresponding rise in the production of active species. And these active species played important role in promoting the conversion of methane (Lee et al., 2015).

Figure 13 Methane conversion while keeping the feed flow rate 200ml/min in plasma alone system.

In the Figure 14, the selectivity of CO₂ and CO are described. With increasing plasma power from 15 to 30, there is a clear trend of higher selectivity towards CO₂ and lower selectivity towards CO. This indicates that higher plasma powers are more effective in achieving complete oxidation of CH₄ to CO₂, rather than partial oxidation to CO. This phenomenon can be explained by delving into the intricacies of plasma chemistry. Methane and oxygen underwent dissociation upon interacting with the high-energy plasma electrons, resulting in the formation of methyl, hydrogen, and oxygen radicals, respectively (Kolb et al., 2013). Notably, during this phenomenon oxygen radicals were not only more reactive but also more abundant compared to methane. Consequently, these energetic oxygen atoms engaged in reactions with CH₃, H, or OH radicals, leading to the production of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water and hydrogen. At lower temperatures, CO was the product of choice, displaying higher selectivity, whereas as the temperature increased, a more abundant generation of CO₂ occurred, stemming from the oxidation of CO to CO₂ (Zhou et al., 1998).

Figure 14 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO. Feed flow rate 200ml/min while changing the plasma powers in plasma alone system.

In the Figure 15, the impact of plasma power on the production of NO_x and N₂O showed. Increasing the plasma power enhances the formation of unwanted gasses. Across all plasma powers NO₂ and N₂O levels escalated while there was not any formation of NO. These outcomes are in line with the findings of prior work by (Penetrante et al., 1997) and (Marques et al., 2008). N₂ molecules dissociated into nitrogen active species and then reacted with the active oxygen and form NO and this NO reacted with the oxygen radical and formed NO₂ (Nguyen et al., 2019).

Figure 15 Formation of NO_x and N₂O. Feed flowrate 200ml/min

8.2.1. Effect of discharge gap

When we conducted experiments using only the plasma-alone system, we observed varying results across the reactors. The reactor A, which had an even gap between electrodes, performed well. The outcomes from this reactor were better than the other. Conversely, the reactors B and C, even when operated under the same conditions as the reactor A, yielded less methane conversion. Moreover, it was visually observed that the strength of the plasma glow inside the reactors B and C was not homogenous and at some parts of the regime the glow was more pronounced than in other parts. At parts where the discharge gap visually larger, the glow was dimmer there. The μ GC results for these three reactors are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 μ GC results for three DBD reactors A, B, C under same experiment conditions.

Power	Inlet vol. %			Outlet vol. %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,51	20,11	77,5	0,17	0,24	0,03
25 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,09	19,26	77,7	0,54	0,30	0
30 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,06	19,17	77,9	0,64	0,25	0
20 W	0,96	20,7	77,02	0,84	20,55	77,1	0,05	0,06	0
25 W	0,96	20,7	77,02	0,44	19,94	77,7	0,24	0,24	0,02
30 W	0,96	20,7	77,02	0,20	19,49	78,05	0,41	0,30	0,03
20 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,96	20,68	76,8	0	0	0
25 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,53	20,09	77,4	0,15	0,25	0,03
30 W	0,96	20,7	76,8	0,25	19,73	77,8	0,34	0,33	0,03

In this experimental study utilizing three quartz glass reactors (A, B, and C), the observed trends in methane conversion and product selectivity revealed distinct performance characteristics as shown in Figures 16, 17 and 18. Reactor A consistently demonstrated higher methane conversion and carbon dioxide production compared to Reactor B and Reactor C across all tested power levels. Conversely, Reactor C exhibited the highest selectivity to carbon monoxide 57 % at 25 W among the three reactors.

Figure 16 Methane conversion, CO₂ and CO selectivity for reactor A (plasma alone system)

Figure 17 Methane conversion, CO₂ and CO selectivity for reactor B (plasma alone system)

Figure 18 Methane conversion, CO₂ and CO selectivity for reactor C (plasma alone system)

In the Figure 19, the NO_x and N₂O formation for these reactors are shown. The trend was same as for the methane conversion. The reactor A generated more unwanted gases than those of other two reactors, which is more likely related to the higher conversion compared to other reactors. The variations in reactor performance underscore the influence of reactor design and power conditions on methane conversion and selectivity to products. As explained by (Van Laer & Bogaerts, 2017), in the DBD reactors with microgap (0,5 mm), the electric field and electron temperature experience a significant augmentation compared to other reactor configurations. This intensified electric field contributes to a higher electron temperature within the reactor. However, there is a trade-off, as this heightened electric field concurrently leads to a reduction in electron density. The lowered electron density has a pronounced impact on the reaction kinetics within the reactor. Specifically, the reaction rate is influenced by the density of the electron. When the density of electron decreases it can consequently affect the overall efficiency and dynamics of the chemical processes occurring in the reactor with smaller gaps.

Figure 19 NO_x and N₂O formations during plasma alone systems under same operating conditions

8.3. Results for plasma-catalysis system

The influence of varying power levels of plasma and by using various catalytic materials inside the reactor on the conversion of methane, was investigated. A range of catalysts, each having distinct compositions and characteristics, was tested in conjunction with plasma powers spanning from 15 W to 30 W. The primary objective was to discern the efficacy of each catalyst-plasma power combination in enhancing methane conversion and selectivity.

8.3.1. Hybridization effect of plasma and γ -Al₂O₃

The γ -Al₂O₃ support was utilized as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Two experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same and the results were almost same. The 1,19 g of catalyst was used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 8, the results are shown.

Table 8 Results from experiments 24 and 25 using γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis.

Power (W)	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20	0,96	20,72	76,86	0,95	20,74	76,96	0,00	0,00	0,00
25	0,96	20,72	76,86	0,63	20,24	77,36	0,15	0,17	0,04
30	0,96	20,72	76,86	0,48	19,98	77,53	0,24	0,22	0,04
20	0,97	20,74	76,97	0,96	20,77	77,07	0,00	0,00	0,00
25	0,97	20,74	76,97	0,68	20,31	77,40	0,13	0,15	0,04
30	0,97	20,74	76,97	0,51	19,99	77,56	0,23	0,23	0,04

In the Figure 20 and 21, the increasing trend of CH₄ conversion and selectivity is shown. The conversion started when the power increased to 25 W. For the maximum power tested the conversion was 65 % while there was not any noticeable increase in the selectivity towards CO₂. When γ -Al₂O₃ was placed inside the plasma zone, it hindered the methane conversion. This may be the result of the catalyst surface's active species produced by plasma being adsorbed and desorbed onto the surface, as well as the reaction area's limited availability (Holzer, 2002).

Figure 20 Methane conversion while keeping the feed flow rate 200ml/min and using γ -Al₂O₃ in plasma-catalysis.

Figure 21 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO. when using γ -Al₂O₃ in plasma-catalysis.

8.3.2. Hybridization effect of plasma and 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃

The 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ was used as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Two experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same and the results were almost same. The 1,2 g of catalyst was used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 9, the results are shown.

Table 9 Results from experiment 07 and 08 using 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis.

Power (W)	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20	0,96	20,67	76,55	0,83	20,44	76,86	0,13	0	0
25	0,96	20,67	76,55	0,53	19,89	77,27	0,42	0	0
30	0,96	20,67	76,55	0,17	19,25	77,78	0,78	0	0
20	0,96	20,66	76,63	0,83	20,44	76,86	0,13	0	0
25	0,96	20,66	76,63	0,62	20,05	77,10	0,39	0	0
30	0,96	20,66	76,63	0,15	19,25	77,92	0,79	0	0

In the Figures 22 and 23, the methane conversion and selectivity for the 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst is shown. The methane conversion trend was similar as it was for the plasma alone system. It was increasing with the increase in the plasma power. But there was not any production of CO. That was the indication of complete oxidation reaction being happened inside the reactor. Moreover, the effect of plasma on the conversion was slightly lower as it was in the plasma alone system. The use of the catalyst inside the plasma zone was found to decrease the methane conversion for the same power levels compared to empty reactor. For example, with the 30 W, the methane conversion was 88 % here but for plasma alone system it was 95 %. This could be because of the several reasons, the consumption of the produced active species by surface reactions. It is possible that oxygen radicals, when encountered the surface of the catalyst, may be worked as a catalyst modifier, and shifted the reaction selectivity towards complete oxidation as explained by (Cordi & Falconer, 1996).

Figure 22 Methane conversion while keeping the feed flow rate 200ml/min and using 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ in plasma-catalysis system

Figure 23 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO, using 1 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ in plasma-catalysis system

8.3.3. Hybridization effect of plasma and 3 % Pd/ γ - Al₂O₃

The 3 % Pd/Al₂O₃ was used as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Two experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same. The 1,18 g of catalyst was used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 10, the results are shown.

Table 10 Results from experiment 09 and 10 using 3 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

Power (W)	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20	0,96	20,72	76,53	0,92	20,63	76,51	0,04	0	0
25	0,96	20,72	76,53	0,90	20,60	76,57	0,09	0	0
30	0,96	20,72	76,53	0,53	19,98	77,20	0,43	0	0
20	0,96	20,65	76,50	0,92	20,56	76,48	0,04	0	0
25	0,96	20,65	76,50	0,85	20,45	76,67	0,11	0	0
30	0,96	20,65	76,50	0,66	20,14	77,03	0,29	0	0

In the Figures 24 and 25, the methane conversion and selectivity for the 3 % Pd/ Al₂O₃ catalyst is shown. As the plasma power raised from 15 to 20 W, there was a slight (5 %) increase in the conversion of methane but when the power was increased to 30 W, about 60 % methane conversion was achieved. While the selectivity for CO₂ was remained maximum with all the plasma powers.

Figure 24 Methane conversion using 3 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

Figure 25 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO using 3 % Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

8.3.4. Hybridization effect of plasma and 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ - Al₂O₃

The 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu /Al₂O₃ was used as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Three experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same. The 1,19 g of catalyst was used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 11, the results are shown.

Table 11 Results from experiment 11, 12 and 21 using 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis.

Power (W)	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20	0,96	20,62	76,61	0,86	20,46	76,79	0,09	0	0
25	0,96	20,62	76,61	0,75	20,24	76,99	0,20	0	0
30	0,96	20,62	76,61	0,49	19,77	77,39	0,46	0	0
20	0,96	20,63	76,71	0,92	20,65	77,04	0,03	0	0
25	0,96	20,63	76,71	0,89	20,52	76,92	0,06	0	0
30	0,96	20,63	76,71	0,78	20,32	77,07	0,18	0	0
20	0,96	20,65	76,57	0,92	20,60	76,65	0,03	0	0
25	0,96	20,65	76,57	0,91	19,96	77,33	0,07	0	0
30	0,96	20,65	76,57	0,74	20,24	76,94	0,20	0	0

In the Figures 26 and 27, the conversion of methane and the selectivity of CO₂ and CO are shown. The methane conversion trend was same as in the previous experiments done with the catalysts. Almost 65 % of conversion achieved at 30 W. There was no any formation of CO.

Figure 26 Methane conversion using 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

Figure 27 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO using 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

8.3.5. Hybridization effect of plasma and 1 % Cu/ γ - Al₂O₃

The 1 % Cu /Al₂O₃ was used as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Two experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same. The 1,17 g of catalyst was

used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 12, the results are shown.

Table 12 Results from experiment 04 and 05 using 1 % Cu/ γ -Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis.

Power (W)	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20	0,96	20,80	76,70	0,79	20,50	76,90	0,11	0,03	0,03
30	0,96	20,80	76,70	0,26	19,54	77,82	0,66		0,03
20	0,96	20,74	76,78	0,59	20,11	77,33	0,30	0,03	0,05
30	0,96	20,74	76,78	0,21	19,42	78,06	0,71	0,02	0,02

In the Figures 28 and 29, the methane conversion and CO₂ selectivity with respect to various plasma powers is shown. At 20 W, the conversion was 51 % and the CO₂ selectivity 54 %. When the power increased to the highest point tested, the conversion was 85 % and the CO₂ selectivity increased to 96 %.

Figure 28 Methane conversion for plasma-catalysis system using 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃

Figure 29 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO using 1 % Cu/γ-Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

8.3.6. Hybridization effect of plasma and 1 % Pt/ γ- Al₂O₃

The 1 % Pt /Al₂O₃ was used as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Two experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same. The 1,12 g of catalyst was used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 13, the results are shown.

Table 13 Result from experiment 19 and 20 using 1 % Pt/γ-Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis.

Power (W)	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20	0,96	20,79	77,00	0,89	20,69	77,10	0,04	0,03	0
25	0,96	20,79	77,00	0,71	20,36	77,52	0,24	0	0
30	0,96	20,79	77,00	0,61	20,11	77,42	0,34	0	0
20	0,96	20,66	76,58	0,89	20,50	76,59	0,03	0	0
25	0,96	20,66	76,58	0,78	20,35	76,85	0,21	0	0
30	0,96	20,66	76,58	0,61	19,99	76,91	0,32	0	0

In the Figures 30 and 31, the conversion of methane and selectivity is provided. At 20 W the conversion was 22 % at the CO₂ selectivity was 45 %. After increasing the power to 30 W the conversion was 57 % and CO₂ selectivity was 97%.

Figure 30 Methane conversion for plasma-catalysis system using 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃

Figure 31 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO using 1 % Pt/γ-Al₂O₃ as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

8.3.7. Hybridization effect of plasma and 1 % Pd-NH₄-ZSM-5

The 1 % Pd-NH₄-ZSM-5 was used as a catalyst inside the reactor plasma zone. Two experiments were performed by keeping the experimental conditions same. The 1,10 g of catalyst was used in both experiments and the flowrate of the feed kept constant at 200 ml/min. In the Table 14, the results are shown.

Table 14 Results from experiment 16 and 18 using 1 % Pd-NH4-ZSM-5 as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

Power	Inlet %			Outlet %					
	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	O ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
20 W	0,97	20,75	77,16	0,96	20,74	77,11	0,00	0	0
25 W	0,97	20,75	77,16	0,88	20,56	77,17	0,08	0	0
30 W	0,97	20,75	77,16	0,84	20,55	77,43	0,12	0	0
20 W	0,96	20,81	77,03	0,96	20,71	77,02	0,00	0	0
25 W	0,96	20,81	77,03	0,87	20,72	77,29	0,09	0	0
30 W	0,96	20,81	77,03	0,83	20,58	77,15	0,12	0	0

In the Figure 32, the conversion of methane is given. At 15 W to 20 W, there was no conversion at all. But when the power increased to 25 W, 31 % conversion was achieved and for 30 W the conversion was 38 %. Regardless of less conversion, the gas that was produced during the reaction was only CO₂ as you can see from the Figure 33.

Figure 32 Methane conversion for plasma-catalysis system using 1 % Pd-NH4-ZSM-5

Figure 33 Selectivity of CO₂ and CO using 1 % Pd-NH₄-ZSM-5 as catalyst in plasma-catalysis system

Summary of the results

In the Figure 34, the comparison of all the catalysts under the same experimental conditions is presented. The data shows a consistent trend: methane conversion generally improved with escalating plasma power, irrespective of the catalyst. However, the extent of improvement and the starting conversion rates are highly contingent upon the catalyst used. Some catalysts, such as 1 % Pd, 1 % Cu with alumina support displayed a synergy with increased power producing only the carbon dioxide and water. But these conversions were lower of that plasma alone system as plasma alone system converted 95 % of methane at 30 W and 1 % Pd on alumina support converted 88 % methane. The extent of oxidation on the metal surfaces plays noticeable role in examining the overall reaction rate. This phenomenon is characterized by terms like weak and strong adsorption of oxygen, as well as the variations in the surface oxide state (Becker et al., 2007). For example, in the case of Pd metal, the PdO is the principal species for methane oxidation as discussed in the Section 4.2 above. Except Pd metal, all other metals loadings on alumina support resulted in the lower conversion of methane but the selectivity towards carbon dioxide was promising. The active metals could also promote the side reactions like water gas shift reaction, methanation which could result in lower conversion of methane (Gao et al., 2021).

Figure 34 Methane conversion while keeping the feed flow rate 200ml/min constant and using the catalysts.

When catalyst is used in the plasma system, the excited methane by electron collisions, is the key species to promote the conversion of methane according to (Nozaki & Okazaki, 2013). When a catalyst was placed into a plasma system, the temperature of vibrationally excited methane changed. In the plasma alone system, the temperature of the reactor at 30 W was 197 °C while in the presence of the catalyst (1 % Pd/ Al₂O₃) the bed temperature was 156°C.

In the Figure 35, the reactor outside temperature in accordance with plasma power is shown. The trend was in increasing manner, as the power increased the bed temperature increased. The energy from the plasma, which was previously dedicated to exciting methane and oxygen molecules, was now shared to activate the catalyst in the plasma-catalysis system. These results align with the research done by (Nozaki et al., 2004). As the catalyst holds importance in the adsorption of active species such as oxygen atoms and excited methane species. The presence of the catalyst impacted on the reaction pathways by which methane was converted in the plasma alone reaction. When there was no catalyst inside the reactor, for example, the plasma power was used to break down methane, resulting in the generation of oxygen radicals. Following that, these radicals undergo both complete and partial oxidation, producing carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide. The reaction routes, however, were altered when catalyst material was inserted into the reactor. Because the catalyst

allowed for more selective reactions, only carbon dioxide was generated, implying a shift in product distribution.

Figure 35 Plasma power vs reactor outside temperature for plasma catalyst system

The Figures 36 and 37, show the CO₂ and CO selectivity for different catalysts. In the case of plasma alone system CO₂ selectivity increased slightly with plasma power while CO selectivity decreased as power increased. The plasma-alone system becomes more selective towards CO₂ and less towards CO as power increases. When 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ was used with plasma CO₂ selectivity improved significantly with power and CO remained at zero across the tested power range. While using 3 % Pd/Al₂O₃ the CO₂ selectivity begins lower but catches up at the highest power. Like the 1% Pd loading, 3% Pd loading is also effective at suppressing CO formation while promoting CO₂. These results are similar as from (Marques et al., 2008). When Pd/ Al₂O₃ is used as catalyst, the active phase of Pd is PdO (Chen et al., 2015). For γ-Al₂O₃ without any metal became slightly selective towards CO at the highest power tested, while CO₂ increased gradually. In comparing the CO and CO₂ selectivity, it seems that catalysts with metals, strongly favor CO₂ formation over CO as explained by (Nkinahamira et al., 2023). This phenomenon exemplified the complicated interplay between plasma and catalyst, in which the catalyst becomes an active participant in the total reaction scheme, impacting not just product distribution but also plasma energy use as explained by (Cordi & Falconer, 1996).

Figure 36 CO₂ selectivity under various catalyst while keeping the Feed flowrate constant 200ml/min and changing the plasma power.

Figure 37 CO selectivity under same experiment condition (Feed flowrate 200ml/min)

NO_x formation

This section describes the NO_x and N₂O formation in the reactor for both systems, when no catalyst was used inside the plasma zone and when catalyst was placed inside the plasma zone.

In Figures 38-40, the formation of NO_x and N₂O gases under plasma alone and plasma-catalysis system is shown. At the lowest plasma power of 15 W, there's a unanimous

observation: no NO_x production occurred across all catalysts and even with plasma alone system. There was no any NO formation for plasma alone, 1% Pd-NH₄-ZSM-5, 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃, 1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/Al₂O₃ and γ -Al₂O₃ plasma-catalysis systems regardless of plasma powers. However, as the plasma power increased, the NO_x formation trend become discernible. By increasing the power, both systems displayed an increase in NO_x formation, particularly the plasma alone and 1% Pd/Al₂O₃ system. This phenomenon was explained by (Baylet et al., 2012). In addition to dissociating methane molecules, the plasma also induced the dissociation of N₂ molecules into nitrogen radicals through processes involving electron impact and vibrational excitation. These nitrogen radicals actively participated in oxidation reactions, which led to the generation of nitrogen oxides and nitrous oxide. The produced NO further undergoes oxidation to NO₂ (Equations listed in the section 5.2).

Figure 38 NO_x and N₂O formation for both systems at 20 W power

Figure 39 NO_x and N₂O formation for both systems at 25 W power

Figure 40 NO_x and N₂O formation for both systems at 30 W power

The trend in NO_x production aligned with the increase in plasma power; as the power was raised, NO_x production also increased. Importantly, the introduction of a catalyst into the system did not impede NO_x production significantly.

9. Error estimation

Possible error sources for used experimental system may arise from the inaccurate calibrations, analysis precision, reactor set-up procedures, and human actions. Before conducting the experiments, the plasma rig, mass flow controllers, temperature measuring devices, and analysis equipment were calibrated accordingly. The analysis equipment FTIR and μ GC were calibrated every week for the accuracy.

During the experiments, three reactors of identical size were used. These reactors were hand made. They had slight variations in the placement of their ground electrodes. This caused the discharge gap to be inconsistent across the reactors. Specifically, one side had a larger gap, while the opposite side was much shorter. When we conducted experiments using only the plasma-alone system, we observed varying results across the reactors. The first reactor (A), which had an even gap between electrodes, performed well. The outcomes from this reactor were better than the other. Conversely, the reactor B and C, even when operated under the same conditions as the reactor A, yielded less methane conversion. Moreover, it was visually observed that the strength of the plasma zone inside these reactors wasn't consistent. On the side with the shorter gap, the plasma zone was stronger compared to the side with the larger gap.

In some of the experiments, no visible plasma glow was observed inside the reactor, when plasma was turned on, at the highest power tested (30 W). Attempts to address that issue, including turning on and off the plasma, proved unsuccessful. Then decision was made to increase the plasma power until there was visible plasma inside the reactor. Notably, at 50 W the plasma became visible. However, this reading dropped to 40 W, and there was no any change in the conversion of methane being monitored by online FTIR and μ GC. Despite the fluctuation, the plasma remained visible and emitted a satisfactory glow even when the power reduced to 30 W. This suggested that the plasma software might occasionally indicate higher power levels than the actual practical values.

The outside reactor and catalyst bed temperatures were monitored with the help of an infrared thermometer. The temperature readings consistently fluctuated based on the specific locations where the thermometer was positioned. To overcome this issue, attempts to use the same location were made. Notably, when catalyst was employed, the potential for hotspots within the catalyst bed introduced additional element to the variability.

Catalysts were placed inside the reactor to cover the plasma zone. Another source of error was attributed to the variation in catalyst weights, where the amount of certain catalyst used inside the plasma zone to cover it, was more than the others.

During online analysis of the gasses, the retention times of certain gasses in some of the experiments were shifted. To address that, manual checks and corrections were conducted on the retention times when necessary. Calibration gas played a crucial role in ensuring the accuracy and optimal functioning of the μ GC and FTIR, aiming to minimize any effects that could cause error.

10. Conclusion and future perspective

The objective of this work was to study whether non-thermal plasma could be used to convert dilute methane in air into less harmful carbon dioxide. The main objective was to explore the effect of catalyst on the hybridized plasma-catalysis system (In-plasma configuration) for methane conversion and selectivity towards complete oxidation while minimizing the NO_x formations was studied.

The experiments were conducted with a continuous laboratory scale DBD reactor. The plasma discharges were created by applying power between inner and outer electrodes. The power was supplied by a power source (PVM500). The plasma power was measured online and determined by external capacitor method with MATLAB-based calculation software. The real time analysis of gasses was performed with FTIR (Gaset FTIR Analyzer) and Agilent micro-Gas Chromatograph (490 μ GC) instrument. Six catalysts were used, including γ -Al₂O₃ support with metals Pd, Cu and Pt and ZSM-5 zeolite with Pd as metal.

According to the experimental findings, the system utilizing only plasma achieved the highest methane conversion (95 %), having both partial and complete oxidation reactions. In contrast, the hybridized system, specifically plasma combined with 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃, exhibited a highest methane conversion (88 %) than all the plasma-catalysis systems. However, the catalyst was found to have a clear effect on the product selectivity by promoting the complete oxidation with no carbon monoxide formation. Notably, there was no noteworthy difference observed in the formation of NO_x in the two systems. Although, the 1 % Pd-NH₄-ZSM-5 produced least NO_x (250 ppm) but the conversion of methane was also only 37 % for the highest power tested (30 W). However, The NO_x formation was prone to be increased with the higher powers of plasma, irrespective of the catalysts used. For plasma alone system at highest power tested (30 W) the NO_x formation was 1094 ppm while for 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ the formation was 1291 ppm.

The observed effect of both plasma power alone and the hybridized system on the methane conversion was aligned with existing literature, i.e., increasing plasma power seemed to enhance the conversion process. When catalyst was placed inside the reactor, the catalyst surface acted as a platform for adsorbing and activating the methane in conjunction with oxygen, facilitating the complete oxidation of methane.

These experiments were conducted using a feed (1 % CH₄ balanced in air) having flowrate of 200 ml/min. Future investigations could explore the impact of varying feed flow rates to assess their impact on methane conversion. Furthermore, altering the gas composition specifically decreasing the methane concentration and then studying the system's response would offer valuable insights. Further research should include in-depth catalyst characterization, particularly examining how plasma influences the surface of the catalyst by employing techniques like XRD. For future experimentations, it is advisable to implement an effective water trapping system to ensure that analysis equipment results remain unaffected by water presence, enhancing the accuracy and reliability.

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APPENDIX 1

In the Table. 1, the experiment list of this study is showed. Feed composition (1 % CH₄ in balanced air) and feed flowrate of 200 ml/min was employed throughout all the experiments.

Experiment	Description	Packing material	Catalyst weight (g)	Reactor
01	Plasma alone	None		A
02	Plasma alone	None		A
03	Plasma alone	None		A
04	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,17	A
05	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,17	A
06	Plasma alone	None		A
07	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,20	A
08	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,20	A
09	Plasma-catalysis	3 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,18	A
10	Plasma-catalysis	3 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,18	A
11	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,19	A
12	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,19	B
13	Plasma alone	None		B
14	Plasma alone	None		B
15	Plasma alone	None		B
16	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd-NH ₄ -ZSM-5	1,10	B
17	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd-NH ₄ -ZSM-5	1,10	B
18	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd-NH ₄ -ZSM-5	1,10	B
19	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pt/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,20	B
20	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pt/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,20	B
21	Plasma-catalysis	1 % Pd-0,5 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,19	B
22	Plasma alone	None		C
23	Plasma alone	None		C
24	Plasma-catalysis	γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,19	C
25	Plasma-catalysis	γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1,19	C

Table. 1 The experiment list for this study

APPENDIX 2

Figure.1 is showing the electrical circuit of dielectric barrier discharge reactor which was utilized in this study.

Figure. 1 Electrical circuit of DBD reactor (VTT)

APPENDIX 3

Figure 2. An example of measured gas composition with FTIR

Figure. 2 Stabilized FTIR results from experiment 05 at 30 W plasma power.

APPENDIX 4

Figure. 3 presents the example of FTIR spectrum.

Figure. 3 FTIR spectrum from experiment 05 at 30 W plasma power

APPENDIX 5

Figure. 4 shows the power calculation software.

Figure. 4 Plasma power calculation software (VTT)